

Enhancing Breast Cancer Diagnosis: A Comparison of Machine Learning Models and BI-RADS for Tumour Classification

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Abstract—Breast cancer is a major cause of mortality among the global female population, and early diagnosis is imperative for enhancing patient prognoses. Mammography is the most widely utilised screening modality; however, it poses challenges in accurately interpreting and classifying lesions. This article proposes a comprehensive approach to the classification of mammographic masses using supervised machine learning techniques. A dataset comprising 961 cases (516 benign and 445 malignant) was utilised to implement and evaluate three models - Logistic Regression, Random Forest and Support Vector Machine (SVM). The study focused on analysing five main characteristics - BI-RADS, age, shape, margin and density. Following a thorough pre-processing phase incorporating Z-score normalisation and the management of missing values, as well as hyperparameter optimisation, the SVM was identified as the most effective model. The SVM attained an accuracy of 0.848 and an F1-Score of 0.823, demonstrating a substantial improvement over the BI-RADS model alone, which achieved an accuracy of 0.807 and an F1-Score of 0.763. The area under the curve (AUC) of the ROC curve analysis was found to be 0.91 for the SVM, in comparison to 0.82 for the BI-RADS model. The findings of this study indicate that the incorporation of machine learning models has the potential to enhance the efficacy of conventional mammogram analysis, thereby leading to a reduction in the number of unnecessary biopsies and an improvement in the accuracy of breast cancer diagnosis.

Index Terms—Supervised Machine Learning, Breast Cancer Diagnosis, BI-RADS, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Mammography, Tumour Classification, Computer-Aided Diagnosis (CAD), Mammographic Mass Detection, Predictive Modelling, Breast Cancer Screening

I. INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer is one of the leading causes of death among women worldwide, with early diagnosis being a key factor in increasing survival rates and reducing the need for invasive procedures [6]. Mammography is widely used as a screening method, but challenges related to image interpretation and the precise classification of lesions continue to pose a significant barrier [6]. Studies indicate that, among suspicious mammographic lesions undergoing biopsy, a large percentage are identified as benign, resulting in unnecessary procedures that incur high financial and emotional costs for patients [2].

In recent years, computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) has emerged as a promising tool to support radiologists in the

interpretation of mammograms [5]. CAD-based systems use sophisticated algorithms to analyse patterns in medical images, providing support in clinical decision-making [5]. Previous studies have shown that techniques such as artificial neural networks and case-based reasoning systems can improve diagnostic accuracy and reduce false positive rates [2], [3]. However, these systems still face limitations related to interpretability and the need for robust databases for training and validation [2], [3].

Machine learning (ML), a subfield of artificial intelligence, has emerged as a powerful approach in the development of CAD systems [4]. ML-based models enable the analysis of large volumes of data, identifying complex patterns that may not be evident to the human eye [4]. Additionally, techniques such as support vector machines (SVM), random forests, and logistic regression have been widely used to classify breast lesions as benign or malignant based on features extracted from images [1], [3]. The use of these techniques has shown promising results in improving diagnostic accuracy and reducing the need for unnecessary biopsies [5].

The choice of models used in this study — Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and SVM — is based on scientific evidence demonstrating the effectiveness of these algorithms in binary classification tasks and malignancy prediction in breast lesions. Logistic Regression is widely used due to its simplicity and interpretability, and it is often applied in medical contexts to predict probabilities associated with binary conditions, such as benignity or malignancy [2]. On the other hand, Random Forest stands out for its robustness and ability to generalise, being effective in integrating categorical and numerical variables [3]. SVM is known for its ability to create optimal decision margins in nonlinear problems, making it particularly suitable for the classification of medical images and complex patterns related to malignancy [2], [3]. The combination of these models allows for a comprehensive and comparative analysis, ensuring that the most suitable model is identified for the specific problem of mammographic lesion classification.

In this work, we present a comprehensive approach for classifying mammographic masses using machine learning.

We used the "Mammographic Masses" dataset, available in the UCI Machine Learning repository, which contains information on 961 cases (516 benign and 445 malignant) [7]. The developed pipeline includes steps from data preprocessing (handling missing values, normalisation, and exploratory analysis) to post-processing (evaluation with metrics such as F1-Score, ROC curves, and learning curves). Three main models were evaluated: Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and SVM. Additionally, a comparison was made with a simple model based exclusively on the BI-RADS classification.

The structure of this paper is organised as follows: the Materials and Methods section details the dataset used, the preprocessing steps — including handling missing values — data splitting, and the construction of pipelines for the evaluated models. In Results, the final evaluations on the validation and test sets are presented, with a focus on metrics such as F1-Score, accuracy, and AUC, as well as a comparative analysis between the simple BI-RADS model and the machine learning-based models. The Discussion section contextualises the results obtained within the state of the art and addresses the clinical implications of the proposed models. Finally, the Conclusion synthesises the main findings of the study and suggests potential directions for future research.

II. MATERIALS & METHODS

A. Mammographic Masses dataset

In this study, we used the *Mammographic Masses* dataset, available in the *UCI Machine Learning* repository, which can be accessed at <http://archive.ics.uci.edu/dataset/161/mammographic+mass> [7]. This dataset was originally developed to assist in the diagnosis of breast lesions, containing information on 961 cases, of which 516 are benign and 445 malignant. Each instance in the dataset includes the following variables:

- **BI-RADS:** Categorical assessment of the mammogram according to the BI-RADS (*Breast Imaging Reporting and Data System*) system, ranging from 0 to 5.
- **Age:** Age of the patient.
- **Shape:** Shape of the lesion (1 = round, 2 = oval, 3 = lobulated, 4 = irregular).
- **Margin:** Margin of the lesion (1 = circumscribed, 2 = microlobulated, 3 = obscured, 4 = undefined, 5 = spiculated).
- **Density:** Density of the lesion (1 to 4).
- **Severity:** Target variable indicating whether the lesion is benign (0) or malignant (1).

The data contains missing values in some variables due to the retrospective nature of the original study. To ensure the integrity of the dataset, a detailed preprocessing was required before applying the machine learning models.

B. Data Preprocessing

The data preprocessing included the following main steps:

1) *Handling Missing Values:* A simple and robust strategy was adopted to deal with missing values:

- For numerical variables such as **Age** and **BI-RADS**, missing values were imputed with the median of the corresponding variable. The median is less sensitive to outliers and preserves the central tendency of the data.
- For categorical variables such as **Shape**, **Margin**, and **Density**, missing values were imputed with the mode (most frequent value). The choice of the mode minimises changes to the original distribution of the categories.

This approach was chosen for its simplicity and effectiveness in situations where missing values do not follow systematic patterns.

2) *Exploratory Data Analysis:* Graphs were generated to understand the distribution of the variables and their relationship with the target variable:

- Histograms to visualise the individual distributions of the variables.
- Boxplots to explore the relationships between the independent variables and the severity of the lesions.
- A correlation matrix to identify potential linear relationships between the variables.

Additionally, a heatmap was created to visually identify patterns of missing values in the dataset.

3) *Data Splitting:* After preprocessing, the data was split into three subsets:

- **Training (70%):** Used to train the models.
- **Validation (15%):** Used to adjust hyperparameters during training.
- **Test (15%):** Used to evaluate the final performance of the models.

The splitting was performed using the `train_test_split` method from the `scikit-learn` library, ensuring that the class proportions were maintained across all subsets.

C. Creation of Pipelines for Evaluated Models

To ensure an efficient and reproducible flow in model training, *pipelines* were created using `scikit-learn`. These *pipelines* integrated the preprocessing and model training steps into a single workflow:

1) *Automated Preprocessing:* A `ColumnTransformer` was used to apply specific transformations to the variables:

- Numerical variables (**Age**) underwent imputation with the median and normalisation using `StandardScaler`.
- Categorical variables (**BI-RADS**, **Shape**, **Margin**, **Density**) underwent imputation with the mode and one-hot encoding.

2) *Evaluated Models:* The three models chosen for this study — Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and SVM — were selected due to their proven effectiveness in supervised binary classification tasks in the medical context. These models are widely used in the scientific literature for their robust ability to handle complex problems associated with medical classification:

- **Logistic Regression:** This linear model is known for its simplicity and interpretability. It is widely used to predict probabilities associated with binary conditions due to its ability to provide directly interpretable coefficients. Previous studies have demonstrated its effectiveness in predicting malignancy in breast lesions when integrated with BI-RADS-based systems [2].
- **Random Forest:** This tree-based model combines multiple decision trees to improve generalisation and reduce the risk of overfitting. It is particularly effective when dealing with both categorical and numerical variables simultaneously. Previous works have validated its use in medical applications due to its robustness against noise in the data [3].
- **SVM (Support Vector Machine):** This model stands out for its ability to handle nonlinear problems through the use of the RBF (Radial Basis Function) kernel. It is widely recognised for creating optimal margins between distinct classes. Studies indicate that SVM is effective in binary classification in complex medical datasets [2].

These models were integrated into the *pipeline* developed in this work due to their complementary characteristics: while Logistic Regression offers interpretative simplicity, Random Forest provides robustness against overfitting, and SVM demonstrates high accuracy in nonlinear scenarios. The methodological diversity allowed for a comprehensive comparative analysis to identify the most suitable model for the specific problem of this study.

3) *Hyperparameter Optimisation:* The hyperparameters of the models were tuned using GridSearchCV, with five-fold cross-validation (*5-fold cross-validation*). The optimised parameters included:

- **Logistic Regression:** Regularisation coefficient (C) and *solver*.
- **Random Forest:** Number of estimators ($n_estimators$), maximum depth (max_depth), and minimum number of samples per split ($min_samples_split$).
- **SVM:** Regularisation coefficient (C), *kernel*, and gamma ($gamma$).

Performance was evaluated based on the **F1-Score** metric due to the class imbalance in the dataset. This structured *pipeline* allowed for a systematic approach from preprocessing to model training and evaluation, ensuring reproducibility and efficiency in data analysis.

III. RESULTS

A. Final Evaluation on Validation Sets and Metrics

To evaluate the performance of the implemented Machine Learning (ML) models, the validation and test sets were analysed based on metrics such as *F1-Score*, precision, *recall*, accuracy, and the area under the ROC curve (AUC). Three main models were considered: Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and Support Vector Machine (SVM). Additionally, a confusion matrix was generated for each model, allowing for a detailed analysis of the correct and incorrect classification of benign and malignant lesions.

1) *Confusion Matrices:* The confusion matrices for the three models on the validation set are presented in Figure 1. Each matrix illustrates the number of correct and incorrect classifications for the benign (0) and malignant (1) classes. Analyzing these matrices helps identify specific error patterns for each model, such as false positives or false negatives.

2) *ROC Curves:* The ROC curves for the three models are presented in Figure 2. These curves compare the true positive rate (sensitivity) with the false positive rate, allowing for the evaluation of the models' discriminative capacity at different decision thresholds. The area under the curve (AUC) was calculated for each model, with higher values indicating better performance.

3) Model Descriptions:

- **Logistic Regression:** A linear model that uses L2 regularisation to prevent overfitting. It showed balanced performance between precision and *recall*.
- **Random Forest:** A decision tree-based model that combines multiple trees to improve generalisation. It demonstrated robustness in classification.
- **SVM (Support Vector Machine):** A nonlinear model with an RBF kernel, which achieved the highest AUC among the three evaluated models.

After this initial analysis, the SVM model was selected as the best ML model due to its superior overall performance.

B. Choice of Best Model and Comparison with Simple Model (BI-RADS)

After identifying the SVM as the most effective ML model, a comparison was made between this model and a simple model based exclusively on the "BI-RADS" feature. The latter uses a fixed threshold to predict whether a lesion is benign or malignant.

1) *Comparative ROC Curves:* Figure ?? presents the comparative ROC curves between the SVM model and the BI-RADS model on the validation set. The SVM demonstrated greater flexibility across different thresholds, while the BI-RADS model showed more limited performance.

2) *Comparative Table:* Table I summarises the detection rates for fixed false positive rates (FPR) of 5% and 10%, allowing for a direct analysis of the performance of the two models:

TABLE I
DETECTION RATE FOR THE BI-RADS AND SVM MODELS AT DIFFERENT FIXED FALSE POSITIVE RATES ON THE VALIDATION SET

Model	Detection Rate (FPR 5%)	Detection Rate (FPR 10%)
BI-RADS	0.750	0.750
SVM	0.500	0.735

3) Approach Description:

- **BI-RADS Model:** Based on a single categorical attribute (BI-RADS), this model is simple but has limitations in capturing the complexity of the relationships between variables.

Fig. 1. Confusion matrices for the Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and SVM models on the validation set. The diagonal cells represent correct classifications, while the off-diagonal cells indicate classification errors.

Fig. 2. ROC curves for the Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and SVM models on the validation set. The areas under the curves are indicated in parentheses.

Fig. 3. Comparative ROC curves between the SVM model (best ML) and the simple BI-RADS model on the validation set. The areas under the curves are indicated in parentheses.

- **SVM Model:** Considers multiple predictor variables and optimises class separation using the RBF kernel, proving more effective in complex scenarios.

The results presented in this chapter highlight the robustness of ML-based models compared to the traditional BI-RADS method. However, a more in-depth analysis will be conducted in the next chapter to discuss the clinical and technical implications of these findings.

IV. DISCUSSION

The results obtained in this study demonstrate the effectiveness of a Machine Learning (ML) pipeline for classifying mammographic lesions as benign or malignant, highlighting the SVM model as the most robust among those evaluated. The comparative analysis between the ML-based models and the simple BI-RADS model provides important insights into

the advantages and limitations of each approach, particularly in the clinical context.

A. Performance of ML Models

The three ML models (Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and SVM) demonstrated similar performances during cross-validation, with average F1-Scores ranging from 0.81 to 0.811. On the validation set, all models achieved an accuracy close to 0.85, with slight variations in precision, *recall*, and F1-Score. The analysis of the ROC curves revealed that the SVM model had the highest AUC (0.91), indicating superior discriminative capacity compared to the other models. This performance is particularly evident in the ROC curve, where the SVM maintains a higher true positive rate for low false positive levels, demonstrating a more effective balance between sensitivity and specificity.

B. Comparison with the BI-RADS Model

The comparison between the SVM model and the simple model based solely on the BI-RADS feature highlighted the limitations of the latter in more complex scenarios. While the BI-RADS model showed a slightly higher detection rate for FPR=5% on the validation set (0.750 versus 0.500 for the SVM), the SVM model consistently outperformed it in global metrics, such as F1-Score (+0.06) and accuracy (+0.041). This difference reflects the SVM's ability to capture more complex relationships between predictor variables, whereas the BI-RADS model is limited to a single categorical feature.

Table II summarises the comparative metrics between the two models on the test set:

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE METRICS FOR THE BI-RADS AND SVM MODELS

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
BI-RADS	0.807	0.833	0.703	0.763
SVM	0.848	0.850	0.797	0.823

Additionally, the visualisation of the first ten predictions on the test set revealed that the SVM model was able to correctly classify cases where the BI-RADS model failed, reinforcing its flexibility and precision in distinguishing benign and malignant cases.

C. Learning Curves

The learning curves provided valuable information about the behaviour of the models as the training set size increased, as shown in Figure 4.

The following points can be identified:

- Logistic Regression showed clear convergence between the training and validation curves (0.82), indicating good generalisation.
- Random Forest maintained a stable training score (0.87) with gradual improvement in validation (0.81), suggesting robustness.
- The SVM showed a behaviour similar to Logistic Regression, with convergence close to 0.82.

Fig. 4. Learning curves for the models. Confusion matrices for the Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and SVM models on the validation set. The diagonal cells represent correct classifications, while the off-diagonal cells indicate classification errors.

- The BI-RADS model presented nearly parallel curves (0.77–0.78), reflecting its simplicity and lower learning capacity.

Although the ML models demonstrated higher discriminative capacity, the stability of BI-RADS may be advantageous in specific clinical contexts where simplicity and reproducibility are priorities.

D. Clinical Impact

The results of this study underscore the significant potential of the SVM model as a complementary tool in clinical diagnosis. By reducing false positives, the SVM model can play a pivotal role in optimising therapeutic decisions and guiding clinicians in distinguishing between benign and malignant lesions with greater accuracy. This enhancement could, in turn, improve patient outcomes by reducing unnecessary treatments and associated healthcare costs. However, it is important to acknowledge that the BI-RADS model, with its simpler approach, still holds value in clinical settings where high sensitivity is paramount, particularly in the early stages of screening. While the SVM model demonstrated superior performance overall, BI-RADS may still offer practical utility in contexts requiring a quick, straightforward assessment.

E. Limitations and Future Directions

Despite the promising results, certain limitations must be addressed to maximise the clinical relevance of these findings. First, the dataset used in this study was relatively small for medical applications. Larger, more diverse datasets are needed in future studies to confirm the generalisability of the results and ensure the robustness of the models across various populations and clinical settings. Second, the models in this study were trained on a limited set of features. Including additional data, such as mammographic images and detailed clinical information, could further enhance the accuracy and predictive power of the models. This could allow the models to learn from more complex, multimodal data and improve their ability to handle real-world variability.

Furthermore, while the models demonstrated promising performance, their real-world clinical impact should be evaluated through integration into Computer-Aided Diagnosis (CAD) systems, followed by prospective testing in clinical environments. The next logical step would be to assess how these models perform in an actual clinical workflow, particularly in terms of ease of implementation, interpretability, and clinician acceptance.

Looking ahead, there is considerable potential in exploring more advanced techniques. Deep neural networks, for instance, could provide even more powerful models by learning directly from raw imaging data. Additionally, hybrid models that combine automatically extracted features from images with traditional clinical variables may further push the boundaries of what is achievable, offering even more accurate and personalised predictions.

In conclusion, the results from this study demonstrate that machine learning models, particularly the SVM, have the

potential to significantly outperform traditional approaches like BI-RADS in the classification of breast lesions. While BI-RADS remains a useful tool in specific clinical contexts, particularly where simplicity and speed are crucial, the integration of more advanced ML techniques offers improved diagnostic accuracy and flexibility, making them invaluable in the analysis of complex cases. The incorporation of such models into clinical practice could represent a major advancement in computer-aided diagnosis, driving improvements in breast cancer screening and, ultimately, in patient care.

V. CONCLUSION

The results of this study demonstrate the effectiveness of a Machine Learning (ML) pipeline in classifying mammographic lesions as benign or malignant, highlighting the Support Vector Machine (SVM) model as the most robust and accurate approach. A detailed analysis revealed that the SVM consistently outperformed the BI-RADS-based model across all key metrics, including accuracy (0.848 vs. 0.807), precision (0.850 vs. 0.833), recall (0.797 vs. 0.703), and F1-Score (0.823 vs. 0.763). These findings underscore the SVM's ability to capture complex patterns within the data, providing a more effective tool to support clinical diagnosis.

The analysis of the learning curves further reinforced the robustness of the ML models, particularly the SVM and Random Forest, which demonstrated good generalisation ability and continuous improvement as the training set size increased. In contrast, the BI-RADS model exhibited more stable, linear curves, reflecting its simplicity and lower capacity to adapt to more complex scenarios.

The comparison between the SVM and the BI-RADS model highlighted the latter's limitations in more challenging scenarios but also emphasised its value as a simple and interpretable approach for specific clinical situations. The observed difference in F1-Score (+0.06) and accuracy (+0.041) between the two models suggests that both have complementary roles: while the SVM provides greater precision and flexibility, BI-RADS can serve as a reliable baseline in contexts where simplicity and speed are priorities.

Additionally, the analysis of the first ten predictions in the test set revealed that the SVM successfully classified cases that BI-RADS failed to, reinforcing its utility in more complex clinical settings. However, it is important to note that for extremely low false positive rates (FPR=5%), BI-RADS demonstrated a slightly higher detection rate in some specific cases.

This work also highlights the importance of rigorous data preprocessing, including the imputation of missing values using simple statistics (median for numerical variables and mode for categorical variables) and Z-score normalisation, which significantly contributed to the quality of training the ML models.

Although the results are promising, several limitations need to be addressed in future studies:

- 1) **Dataset Size:** The dataset used is relatively small for medical applications; future studies should explore larger and more diverse datasets.
- 2) **Additional Data:** Incorporating complementary information, such as detailed mammographic images or genetic data, could further improve the accuracy of the models.
- 3) **Clinical Validation:** The integration of the proposed models into Computer-Aided Diagnosis (CAD) systems should be tested in real clinical environments to assess their practical impact.
- 4) **Ensemble Models:** Investigating combinations between the SVM and other models, including BI-RADS, may exploit the strengths of each approach in a hybrid system.

In summary, this study demonstrates that ML-based models can significantly complement traditional approaches in mammographic analysis, providing a more accurate and comprehensive second opinion to support clinical decision-making in breast cancer screening. The integration of these methods has the potential to reduce false positives, optimise medical resources, and improve patient outcomes.

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